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Research and Development Expenditure in the Public Sector in Italian Regions

It decreased by an average of 2.81% between 2018 and 2023

All research and development expenditures in the public sector (GOVERD) and higher education sector (HERD) (Eurostat). Research and development expenditure is one of the main drivers of economic growth in a knowledge-based economy. Therefore, trends in the R&D expenditure indicator provide key insights into the future competitiveness and wealth of the EU. R&D expenditure is essential for transitioning to a knowledge-based economy, as well as for improving production technologies and stimulating growth. The value is expressed as a percentage of GDP. The data refer to the Italian regions for the period between 2018 and 2023.

Public Sector Research and Development Expenditure in 2023. The data on public sector research and development (R&D) expenditure, expressed as a percentage of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for various Italian regions in 2023, provide a significant snapshot of regional priorities in innovation and technological development investments. There is marked diversity among the regions, with Lazio standing out for the highest investment in R&D, reaching 122.1993% of GDP. This exceptionally high figure perhaps underscores an intense concentration of public and private research activities, potentially influenced by the presence of numerous institutes and universities, as well as the proximity of major Italian institutions. At the same time, regions like Sardinia and Friuli Venezia Giulia demonstrate significant commitments to research, both exceeding 100% of GDP. These investments may reflect strategies aimed at compensating for structural or economic limitations through innovation and technological development. In contrast, Valle d'Aosta is at the opposite end of the spectrum, with R&D expenditure representing only 37.68573% of GDP, suggesting a different allocation of public resources or an economic fabric less focused on pure and applied research. Regional discrepancies can stem from various factors, including the local industrial fabric, the presence of universities and research centers, local investment policies, and regional strategic priorities. For example, Lombardy, despite being one of Italy's most economically vigorous regions, shows a relatively low percentage of R&D expenditure (53.9403%), which could indicate a greater emphasis on other types of economic investments or a strong integration with the private R&D sector. In conclusion, these data highlight not only the strategic importance that different regions attribute to research and development but also how such investments can be influenced by a complex interplay of economic, social, and political factors. They raise interesting questions about the effectiveness of such investments in terms of results achieved and how different regions balance the needs for immediate development with long-term investments in knowledge and innovation.

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Public Sector Research and Development Expenditure in Italian Regions between 2018 and 2023. Analyzing the data on public sector research and development expenditure as a percentage of GDP between 2018 and 2023 in various Italian regions, we can observe several interesting trends. First, there is significant variety among the regions in terms of changes in expenditure. Some regions, such as Friuli Venezia Giulia, have seen a significant increase in expenditure (+7.128%), reaching 100% of their R&D expenditure relative to GDP, suggesting a strong commitment to innovation and development. Trentino Alto Adige also recorded a notable increase (+12.634%), demonstrating significant dynamism in the research sector. In contrast, regions like Calabria and Puglia experienced concerning declines, -18.841% and -16.721% respectively, indicating perhaps difficulties in maintaining R&D investments or a redistribution of resources to other sectors. It is interesting to note that the region with the highest absolute expenditure in 2018, Lazio, saw a slight decrease (-2.684%) while remaining at relatively high levels. This could reflect a stabilization of investments after periods of strong expansion. Some regions maintained a certain stability, such as Veneto, where the percentage change was 0%. This could indicate a policy of continuity in R&D investments.

North-South Divide. From the data provided on public sector research and development (R&D) expenditure as a percentage of GDP between 2018 and 2023 in various Italian regions, a trend suggesting the existence of a North-South divide in investment in this area emerges. Northern regions, such as Friuli Venezia Giulia and Trentino Alto Adige, have recorded significant increases in their R&D expenditure. Friuli Venezia Giulia, in particular, has reached R&D expenditure equal to 100% of its GDP, while Trentino Alto Adige has seen an increase of 12.634%, both signs of a strong commitment to innovation and research. Conversely, many Southern regions have shown significant decreases or very modest increases. Calabria and Puglia, for example, have experienced significant reductions in their R&D expenditure, with declines of -18.841% and -16.721% respectively. These data suggest that these regions may have difficulties maintaining or increasing investments in research and development. However, there are important exceptions that contradict a clear-cut and uniform division between North and South. For instance, Sardinia in the South saw a 4.159% increase in R&D expenditure, demonstrating a commitment to research and innovation. Despite these exceptions, the general trend suggests that Northern regions tend to have a greater capacity or willingness to invest in R&D compared to many Southern regions. This divide can be influenced by various factors, including the different distribution of economic resources, the presence of universities and research centers, and regional policies focused on innovation and technological development. In summary, the data suggest the existence of a North-South divide in research and development investment in Italy, although there are important exceptions indicating a more nuanced and complex reality.

Economic Policies to Increase Public Sector Research and Development Expenditure in Italian Regions. To increase research and development (R&D) expenditure in the public sector as a percentage of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Italian regions, a series of targeted economic policies are necessary. An effective approach could begin with promoting partnerships between universities, research institutions, and private enterprises, encouraging collaboration in R&D projects through tax incentives and financial support. Regions could establish innovation funds dedicated to supporting applied research and technological development in areas considered strategic for local economic development. Another tool could be the implementation of "innovation zones," geographical areas where companies investing in R&D can benefit from favorable conditions, such as lower bureaucratic

and fiscal burdens. Education also plays a fundamental role: investing in higher and postgraduate education in key fields for innovation can ensure the growth of a highly qualified human capital capable of actively contributing to R&D. Additionally, enhancing digital and technological infrastructures is a prerequisite for an advanced research environment, allowing for wider dissemination and application of research results. The adoption of public procurement policies that favor the purchase of innovative goods and services can stimulate demand for innovation, creating a virtuous circle that further fuels R&D investments. Finally, establishing a constant dialogue between the public and private sectors is crucial to align R&D efforts with market needs and social priorities, ensuring that investments are directed towards key sectors for sustainable development and innovation. Through these policies, Italian regions can not only increase R&D expenditure as a percentage of GDP but also stimulate long-term economic growth and competitiveness.

Conclusions. Public sector research and development expenditure decreased by an average of 2.81% between 2018 and 2023, from 81.76 to 78.88. The regions where R&D expenditure increased the most between 2018 and 2023 are Trentino Alto Adige with +12.36% and Friuli Venezia Giulia with +7.12%. However, there are also regions where this value significantly decreased, namely Puglia with -16.72% and Calabria with -18.84%. Looking at the macro-regions, we can note that on average, Central Italy regions in 2023 spent a value of 89.32, higher than the same value for the South, which was 82.02, and the North at 70.54. However, these values are expressed as a percentage of GDP. Additionally, these values do not exhaust the total economic resources that can be invested in research and development. Indeed, to these values identified in the public sector, we must add the financial resources of the private sector. Summing the R&D expenditure of both the public and private sectors, a higher level of funding can be achieved.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix